

TYPES OF STYLISTIC CONNOTATIVE EXPRESSIVENESS

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ABSTRACT

Expressiveness is a generic linguistic category and as such it is inherent in all language level, as well as appropriate linguistic units. On a broad scale, expressiveness is defined as a magnification of the speech figurativeness and expression. In modern linguistics expressiveness is related to the interaction of the emotional.

Keywords: *category of expressiveness, category of tension, category of evaluation, category of emotiveness, language and speech, language system, transmitter and receptor, expression and figurativeness.*

INTRODUCTION

One of the primary domains of modern Linguistics is the Syntactic Expressiveness. It is a distinctive interdisciplinary subject interweaving a number of disciplines, such as syntax, stylistics and the study of expressiveness. Having achieved a certain degree of autonomy, in recent years this discipline has elaborated its specific methodological and conceptual apparatus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Language being the main tool of communication is not a mere means of information transfer, but also the way of expressing the subjective attitude of the speaker to the utterances. As initiated by R. Jakobson there have been singled out six

language functions, namely referential, poetic, emotive, conative, phatic and metalingual [2]. Thought conceived in speech and hence the text, adorned by different gradations of expressive behavior and tension, is the result of the emotive language function, perceived as “the emotional state of the speaker, his/her subjective attitude towards the phenomena and objects of extralinguistic reality” [1]. It is worth mentioning that expressiveness is one of the key problems in linguistics, since it is directly related to the individual perspective of human language, particularly the speaker’s emotional attitude to the utterance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

“Expressiveness” is a cluster of semantic- stylistics features of a linguistic unit, and these features enable the given linguistic unit to convey the subjective attitude of the speaker to the content of the utterance or the addressee in speech. It can be characterized as a “logically non-disintegrated unit” with supplementary loading as related to the lexical or grammatical unit or as an enhancement, highlighting of a meaning. It can also be interpreted as an expressive component of the meaning, a parallel meaning of the referential meaning, which reveals the subjective emotional, personal evaluation of the word. Given the above-mentioned hints at the multi-faceted nature of the phenomenon in question, it cannot cover the whole spectrum of the features of expressiveness. Expressiveness is such a semantic category which ensures the transmission of the speaker’s attitude via the exterior and interior factors. The nature of the category of expressiveness is the transmission of additional semantic connotations as augmented to the lexical and grammatical meaning with the aim of enhancing it.

Generalizing different views on “expressiveness” in modern linguistics, it is obvious that “expressiveness” is interpreted along with [4]:

1. emotionality and evaluation;
2. figurativeness, tension and stylistic coloring;
3. quantitative loading;

4. imagery.

All these subcategories never function separately, but rather they co-function bringing about emotionalilty, evaluation and tension. Research shows that the classification and re- occurrence of these subcategories varies across different text genres and the specific approach of the researchers. For example, “emotionality” can re-occur with “evaluation”, “figurativeness”, and “stylistic coloring”; “evaluation” can go with “emotionality”; “figurativeness”, “tension”, “stylistic markedness”; “figurativeness ” is accompanied by “tension”, “emotionality”, “stylistic markedness”, “horizontal peculiarities of the text” and so on.

Any means of expression has explicit and implicit evaluation. This is how the category of expressiveness is related to the category of evaluation. Evaluation is present in any situation and act wherein the subject cognizing the world deals with the objective reality. Linguistics has borrowed the concept of “evaluation” from “logic of evaluation”, where evaluation is perceived as an utterance about values. Often evaluation is quite fairly interpreted as a subjective category, assuming that the nature of evaluation is to express subjective attitude towards the extralinguistic reality, neglecting features of objective reality.

The category of expressiveness, a sophisticated notion, comes forth only in conjunction with tension. In modern linguistics there are various terms to refer to this category, such as “grading”, “gradation”, “scaling”, “Intensivierung”, “Verstaerkung”, “Steigerung”, “Graduierung”, “Grad” ansion have been investigated based on tnd others.

CONCLUSION

Taking into consideration the interpretations of the linguistic category of expressiveness in modern literature and adhering to different views, the interrelation of expressiveness with other linguistic categories such as emotionality, evaluation, and tension, can be reiterated as follows:

1. “Expressiveness” is the enhancement of the utterance, its figurativeness and illocutionary force.

2. "Expressiveness" is classified among the means of subjective modes of communication.
3. Evaluation is a linguistic category which reflects the speaker's/writer's evaluation of certain objects or phenomena of the objective reality.
4. Tension is a linguistic category which reflects and nominates the objective quantitative characteristics of this or that attributive feature. Tension indicates the quantitative nature of this or that phenomenon or object.

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